

SYSTEMATIC ANALYSIS OF FAMOUS NAMES IN SCIENTIFIC AND ARTISTIC ONOMASTICS

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Abstract: Systematic analysis of onomastics from a scientific and artistic point of view was the main goal of this study. That is why this section of "Uzbek onomastics" attracts the attention of researchers with its unique problems and urgent problems that need to be solved. Therefore, in this field, the main attention is paid to the methodology of nouns as artistic onomastic units. Because positive images in popular scientific and artistic works created symbolic images of beloved heroes in the vernacular, and their names became popular among the people. So, the problems of Uzbek artistic onomastics are an area where large-scale scientific research can be successfully carried out.

Introduction. We know that "Onomastics" and "Uzbek onomastics" are divided into several large branches. One such large branch is "Uzbek artistic onomastics". Its units are the unique wealth of our mother tongue, as they are considered onomastic units. The reason is that "...self-awareness, the expression of national consciousness and thinking, the spiritual-spiritual connection between generations is manifested through language. All good qualities are absorbed into the human heart, first of all, by the unique charm of the mother tongue. The mother tongue is the soul of the nation."

We would like to emphasize here that we can use selected works of art from ancient times to the present day to find a scientific solution to the scientific

theoretical and practical problems of "Uzbek artistic onomastics". Of course, the set of onomastic units selected from them should be interpreted, described and classified based on scientific principles. After all, if there are reasonable and reliable materials for any auspicious purpose, its implementation will be reasonable and reliable.

Materials and Methods. At this point, it is necessary to mention that E.Begmatov and his students made observations in scientific and practical directions in the field of the technique of noble horses. E.Qilichev, without talking about the issues and problems of Uzbek artistic onomastics, in the study guide prepared for a special course called "Onomastics of the Uzbek language", the role of onomastic units in the language dictionary system, the folk history of anthroponyms, in particular, the history of names, the expression of systemic relations between words in anthroponyms, anthropogenic indicator and the interpretation and analysis of the stylistic features of anthroponyms, the uniqueness of anthroponyms in the works of S.Ayniy, the stylistic features of anthroponyms in the works of A.Qahhor which serves to reveal the idea of the work, the anthroponyms used in the text of the epics of E. Jumanbulbul, including the stylistic features of toponyms, synonyms, hydronyms and oronyms problems are subjected to scientific analysis.

Along with "Uzbek nomology", which is one of the special forms of nomology, it also has several types, such as folk onomastic, scientific onomastic, and artistic onomastic. The reason is that there are folk onomastics, scientific onomastics, and artistic onomastics as one of different cases of nouns. They have individual usage norms. In order to know the level, scope of application and use of these norms, it is necessary to conduct scientific research on special scientific theoretical content on Uzbek artistic onomastics.

Results and discussion. At this point, it is necessary to think about the naming, renaming, and use of the nouns found in the texts of artistic works in Uzbek literature, and their methodology, which expresses the integrity of the

standards of their pronunciation and use. In the press, in everyday life, on radio, on television, and in artistic works, in particular, in the text of the works of creators, the individual manifestations of the processes of using different and different meaningful nouns are unique individual methods. That is why the methodology of nouns in the language, more precisely, in the lexicology specific to the language, differs to a certain extent from the methodologies of other fields.

In contrast to similar nouns in the appellative lexicon, the objects of the proper nouns in the onomastic lexicon, from various points of view, together with the characteristic of naming, indicate that they are also characterized by expressiveness, emotionality, demonstrativeness, i.e., stylistic features. Because folk onomastics requires the oral communication style, and scientific onomastics requires analysis and interpretations in a scientific style, while artistic onomastics, without words, shows the characteristics of onomastic units specific to the artistic style and prepares for scientific analysis.

Conclusion. Also, the wise, faithful, loyal, intelligent, strong, resilient and kind characters in the epics of Alisher Navoi's "Hamsa", the name Babur in "Boburnoma" and "Starry Nights", Otabek and Kumush in "Bygone Days", Anvar in "Mehrobdan Chayan" and Rana, Alisher Navoi in the novel "Navoiy", Saida Alieva in "Sinchalak", father figure and child in the works of Gafur Ghulom, Ulug'bek in "Treasure of Ulugbek", mother figure in the works of O'tkir Hashimov, because of their unique reality, embodying the hopes and dreams of the people in their names. at the same time, there is no doubt that it is important from educational and educational, scientific theoretical, and scientific-practical aspects. No matter how much we repeat these as materials of Uzbek artistic onomastics, we should not forget that they are one of the research objects of linguistics.

In naming babies born today, the names of the main positive characters in popular literary works are also recognized to a certain extent and are of great importance as one of popular names. Because positive characters in popular literary and artistic works create symbolic images of beloved heroes in the

language of the people, their names have become popular among the people. So, the problems of Uzbek artistic onomastics are a field in which it is possible to successfully carry out great scientific research that is waiting for its solution.

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